

FINANCIAL LITERACY A CASE STUDY OF ADILABAD DISTRICT CO-OPERATIVE CENTRAL BANK LIMITED

Prof. R. Venkateswar Rao*¹, Dr. M. Sathya Shivalini*²

*^{1,2}Bussiness Management/ Osmania University, India.

ABSTRACT

Due to rapid growth in Indian economy over the last decade and expansion of financial markets through privatization, liberalization, and globalization have given a way to overabundance of financial products and services in banking, investing, borrowing saving and other etc. Low level of financial literacy prevents individual from making right choices regarding financial decisions, to achieve the objectives, individual must invest his or her saving in right investment alternatives, the objectives of the study is to investigate into the financial literacy among respondents' Age group, Gender, Occupation, Educational Qualification and monthly income. It is found that financial literacy in Adilabad District is very low and necessitates exertion to mend level of literacy. Finally, the issues discussed in this paper open up several avenues for future research.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Financial Attitude, Financial Knowledge, Financial Behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

Literacy has been considered as one of the prime indicators for the social-economic development of the people. The literacy rate of any district, state and country reflect the social, economic and political status of the respective region. The literacy rate varies from region to region and increases with time. According to 2011 cents average literacy rate of India is 74.04% and the average literacy rate of the Adilabad district is 75.63%.

Adilabad district is the second largest district of Telangana state in India. Adilabad District has a total of 7 Revenue Divisions, 52 Mandals, 23 Towns and 1748 Villages. The district has a total area of 16,105 sq. km., 353.7 sq. km is urban and 15751.3 sq. km is rural. The district population in 2021 is 29, 68,247. As per the 2011 census of India, Adilabad has a population of 27, 41,239. The male population are 13, 69,597 and female population are 13, 71,642. Literate people are 14, 83,347 out of 8, 56,350 are male and 6, 26,997 are female. People living in Adilabad District depends on multiple skills, total workers 13, 23,667 out of which men are 7, 48,939 and women are 5, 74,728. A total of 3, 43,500 cultivators are dependent on agriculture farming out of 2, 20,624 are cultivated by men and 1, 22,876 are women. 3, 32,524 people work for agricultural land as labor, men are 156351 and 1, 76,173 are women. Out of the total population of Adilabad in the district, that 7, 60,259 are in an urban area and 19, 80,980 are in a rural area. 1, 76,839 households are in urban, 4, 73,010 are in rural area. 5, 17,640 literate people are in urban, 9, 65,707 are in rural area. The Mandal wise villages, population, literacy rate and illiteracy rate details are given below:

Sl. No.	Mandals	Villages	Population 2011	Literacy (%)	Illiteracy (%)
1	Adilabad	43	1,98,338	55.29	44.71
2	Asifabad	61	58,511	77.26	22.74
3	Bazarhathnoor	31	28,911	52.19	47.81
4	Bejjur	46	49,284	39.75	60.25
5	Bela	47	38,318	62.38	37.62
6	Bellampally	13	80,897	73.39	26.61
7	Bhainsa	34	89,417	54.00	46.00
8	Bhimini	35	26,285	39.49	60.51
9	Boath	39	48,216	53.63	46.37
10	Chennur	34	54,692	60.25	39.75
11	Dahegaon	39	34,712	63.34	36.66

12	Dandepalle	31	49,741	66.00	34.00
13	Dilawarpur	31	35,780	47.17	52.83
14	Gudihathnur	21	30,339	62.46	37.54
15	Ichoda	42	52,840	60.94	39.06
16	Indervelly	34	47,506	66.78	33.22
17	Jainad	55	47,904	58.48	41.52
18	Jainoor	18	31,453	52.56	47.44
19	Jaipur	35	50,079	53.84	46.16
20	Jannaram	26	52,883	57.27	42.73
21	Kaddam (Peddur)	38	52,703	48.00	52.00
22	Kagaz Nagar	38	1,10,078	70.35	29.65
23	Kasipet	21	32,749	61.20	38.80
24	Kerameri	46	30,724	42.71	57.29
25	Khanapur	32	61,984	60.25	39.75
26	Kotapalle	37	33,110	62.74	37.26
27	Kouthala	30	50,938	46.30	53.70
28	Kubeer	38	47,984	53.29	46.71
29	Kuntala	28	34,190	52.25	47.75
30	Laxmanchanda	22	36,739	50.06	49.94
31	Lokeshwarm	31	34,253	44.30	55.70
32	Luxttipet	21	50,674	64.96	35.04
33	Mamada	33	32,303	60.54	39.46
34	Mancherial	27	1,95,228	71.90	28.10
35	Mandamarri	11	1,00,109	61.00	39.00
36	Mudhole	40	55,923	48.54	51.46
37	Narnoor	54	49,239	54.72	45.28
38	Nennel	29	23,534	47.43	52.57
39	Neradigonda	43	29,633	49.40	50.60
40	Nirmal	38	1,39,570	67.62	32.38
41	Rebbena	31	35,859	52.75	47.25
42	Saragangapur	28	48,820	47.30	52.70
43	Sirpur	26	26,097	50.29	49.71
44	Sirpur (T)	26	31,130	47.55	52.45
45	Talamadugu	28	34,632	53.06	46.94
46	Tamsi	31	39,631	50.44	49.56
47	Tandur	24	32,617	78.00	22.00
48	Tanoor	33	39,752	50.48	49.52
49	Tiryani	40	26,410	47.24	52.76

50	Utnoor	39	63,465	63.77	36.23
51	Vemanpalle	33	19,532	64.63	35.37
52	Wankidi	37	35,523	48.68	51.32

Adilabad district is a total area of 16105 sq. KMs. After Mahabobnagar having 16128sq KMs. Nearly about half of the district from North-East to South-West is situated on rocky east crust less amenable for agriculture with very poor irrigation facilities and with deep water. Purchasing anything of the people in this area has to live with little agriculture sources they have. Hence their primary concern is to earn, something, livelihood their economy has been “Hand to mouth”.

The district has a predominant population of tribal people who lives in hills and rocky places. They depend on small crops for their survival. In the Adilabad district where tribal people lives there are some villages located in agency areas that are non-tribal people belonging to the SC category they do not have lands for cultivation and they are labors and the percentage of illiteracy comes from these areas. Even they do not have bank accounts. They have limited transport facilities speed over North-East to South-West. Important tribal people are Gonds, Koyas, Naikpond and Pradhans and Lambada. As per the 2021 census, the percentage of ST population is 18.1 of the total population, the majority population of tribes live in the place of hills and forest stretched from North East to South West region of the district. The land is not so fertile and located in a rocky belt with a poor water facility.

The coal belt is stretching from Sirpur-Kagaznagar to Mancherial. It is an industrial area, Coalmines, Limestone, Mines, Cement paper industries lie in this area. The other part from Luxettipet to Sarangapur is agriculture based; Nirmal town has been a cultural center of Adilabad district. There are many beedi factories in the Nirmal region. One of the largest components that provide the hub of the rural economy is agriculture. It consists of, cultivation of crops of various kinds of cereals, pulses, fruits, vegetables; oilseeds etc. Finance is the vital requirement that supports the main economic activity which forms the pulse of Adilabad district.

There are 356 various bank branches along with 42 Adilabad District Co-operative Bank Limited (ADCCB) branches and 60 Primary Agricultural Co-operative Societies (PACS) in the district to support the rural people in financial inclusion.

The Adilabad District Co-operative bank in Adilabad has a history of almost 80 years. In India, cooperative banks play an important role even today in rural financing. The business of co-operative banks in urban areas also has increased phenomenally in recent years due to a sharp increase in the number of Primary agriculture co-operative societies (PACS). Credit is a crucial input process of development.

RBI and NABARD have taken several initiatives through cooperative banks for promoting financial literacy among rural people. The study will provide an insight into rural banking in selected villages of the Adilabad district. The purpose is to know how cooperative banks work for promoting financial literacy in rural areas of the Adilabad district.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Reddy, M. M., Akhila, M., Arundhathi, C., Bharathwaj, S. S. B., & Deepak, N. (2017): Financial literacy offers with huge implications of nation’s monetary nicely being and its augmentation. The trouble of lack of economic literacy is now not solely with the growing international locations however additionally with developed countries. The OECD (March 2015) described economic literacy as “A mixture of awareness, acquaintance, skill, mind-set and conduct vital to make sound monetary choices and eventually gain person economic properly - being.” The existing find out about is aimed at reading the appreciation of rural households toward economic literacy and to discover the cognizance on line banking offerings (going digital) amongst the rural households in Karimnagar District of Telangana State. The learn about discovered that the majority of the rural households have their financial institution debts in Public Sector Banks (60%) and about 50 per cent of the rural households who do now not have banking and ATM amenities have to tour under 5 km and about 50 per cent have to tour a distance of 5 to 10 km in order to avail banking and ATM services. Further, it is found that the majority of the rural households opined that their most desired funding preference is Bank Deposits (55%) and an overwhelming majority of the rural households i.e., eighty four per cent mentioned that they are no longer conscious of something about inventory market. The learn about concludes that the government, coverage

makers, regulatory bodies, banks, insurance plan companies, NGOs and educationists and college students ought to contain in more than a few cognizance programs so as to enhance the monetary literacy in city areas in widespread and in rural areas in unique which in flip helps in boom of the economic system as a whole.

Priya, R.: Financial literacy of an individual's is their stage of perception of economic things which permits them to technique economic facts and makes knowledgeable selections about private finance. It is hard for a frequent man to apprehend the danger related with the new age economic products. In order to apprehend threat and return related with these products, a minimal degree of economic literacy is a must. Financially literate persons can make high-quality use of these economic merchandise and offerings with the aid of evaluating related dangers and returns and ultimately deciding on these merchandise which are nice appropriate to them. An try has been made via this article to take a look at the relationship between monetary literacy of salaried persons and their consciousness concerning monetary products. In addition, the relationship between monetary literacy and funding conduct of salaried folks is studied. The outcomes of the find out about propose that economic literacy degree of people influences the cognizance as nicely as funding preferences of salaried persons toward economic products.

Vittal, B., & Reddy, M. K. (2019). Literacy is the key for socio-economic progress. Although literacy fees are increased after the independence, the stage of literacy is nonetheless under the world common literacy price of 84% and of all nations. India presently has the biggest illiterate population. Despite governments' motivation, India's literacy fee extended solely sluggishly and current lookup literature suggests that it would take till 2060 for India to reap everyday literacy at then-current charge of progress. The contemporary survey of 66th spherical of NSS estimates point out that in 2009-10, much less than two-thirds (66.8%) of the populace of all a while have been literate. The standard disparity in literacy throughout the populace is heightened through the presence of rural- city and male-female disparity. This paper analytically discusses the literacy charges and instructional degree of special social organizations primarily based upon a variety of rounds of NSSO estimates. This paper has been divided into three levels. In the first stage literacy fee amongst Telangana states of Top districts which includes Rural and Urban areas is discussed. In the 2nd degree increase fee of literacy from India was once presented. In the 1/3 stage comparative find out about of literacy price from Telangana country and India is presented. In the remaining stage statistical evaluation and forecasting of Literacy fee the usage of Holt's Exponential Smoothing technique is used.

Amit K in his study (2001): The study "Appraisal of a rural Co-operative with the trust on rural development: an empirical study" The study reveals that the rural co-operative banks have been able to improve the living standard of the rural people of the studied area, thus the rural co-operative banks accelerated the process of rural development in remote India.

N.K. Thingalaya, I.N. Tewary: In his study, he found that loans are now not appropriate used with the aid of beneficiaries due to a lack of knowledge, possibilities and will. They use to waste the mortgage on consuming and ingesting and accordingly the cause of the mortgage is defeated.

Balishter and Singh (2001): He made an try to have a look at the overall performance of cooperative banks in rural improvement and the overall performance used to be examined via the borrowing of cooperative banks in the improvement of rural infrastructure facilities, grant of savings and organizing the advertising and processing activities. But it was once located that the overall performance was once no longer up to the mark due to numerous weaknesses, i.e., useful resource constraint, giant past due and faulty management.

Study objectives and Hypothesis:

- The study objectives:

Are investigated into the financial literacy among respondents' Age group, Gender, Occupation, Educational Qualification and monthly income.

- Study Hypothesis:

1. There is no association of financial literacy among respondents Age group.
2. There is no association of financial literacy among respondents Genders.
3. There is no association of financial literacy among respondents Occupation.
4. There is no association of financial literacy among respondents Educational Qualification.

5. There is no association of financial literacy among respondents Monthly Income.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study based on both primary and secondary data. A primary survey conducted with 100 rural households from villages of Adilabad District. Five villages have selected from the Adilabad district. From each village 20 people have taken for this study. The selection of respondents based on a simple random sampling technique.

DATA ANALYSIS:-

		F	%
AGE GROUP	<20 yrs.	15	15.0%
	21-30 yrs.	44	44.0%
	31-40 yrs.	26	26.0%
	41-50 yrs.	8	8.0%
	>50 yrs.	7	7.0%
	Total	100	100.0%
Gender	Male	82	82.0%
	Female	18	18.0%
	Total	100	100.0%
Occupation	Farmer/Agricultural Labor	31	31.0%
	Self Employed	52	52.0%
	Non-Agricultural Labor	11	11.0%
	Unemployed	6	6.0%
	Total	100	100.0%
Educational Qualifications	Illiterate	24	24.0%
	Metric	45	45.0%
	10+2/ Intermediate	13	13.0%
	Less than Graduate	18	18.0%
	Total	100	100.0%
Monthly Income (Rs.)	Up to 5000	17	17.0%
	Rs.5001-10000	44	44.0%
	10001-15000	11	11.0%
	15001 and above	28	28.0%
	Total	100	100.0%
	Total	100	100.0%

This sample of hundred respondents contains 82 male and 18 female respondents which make-up for 82 and 18 percentage respectively. The largest group of respondents that is (45%) with Metric degree the smallest group of respondents (13%) with a 10+2/ intermediate. 44% of the respondents are with (21-30) years old while 7% less than fifty years old leaving the remaining into other smaller years of Age group Based on the objectives and hypotheses of the study, the researchers applied the ANOVA test at 5% level of significance to test the association of financial literacy among respondents Age group.

-H1 stat that, " **There is no association of financial literacy among respondents Genders**".

ANOVA					
FinancialLiteracy					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3.979	4	0.995	3.194	0.017
Within Groups	29.582	95	0.311		
Total	33.561	99			

The statistical output showed a p-value of 0.017 which is less than 0.05 and hence Null hypothesis is rejected. ANOVA test proved that, "there is relation between financial literacy and the respondents Age group. -H2 stat that, " **There is no association of financial literacy among respondents Genders**".

ANOVA					
FinancialLiteracy					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.447	1	0.447	1.323	0.253
Within Groups	33.114	98	0.338		
Total	33.561	99			

The statistical output showed a p-value of 0.253 which is less than 0.05 and hence Null hypothesis is rejected. ANOVA test proved that, "there is relation between financial literacy and the respondents Genders. -H3 stat that." **There is no association of financial literacy among respondents Occupation**".

ANOVA					
FinancialLiteracy					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12.473	3	4.158	18.927	0.000
Within Groups	21.088	96	0.220		
Total	33.561	99			

The statistical output showed a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 and hence Null hypothesis is accepted. ANOVA test proved that, "there is no relation between financial literacy and the respondents Occupations. -H4 stat that." **There is no association of financial literacy among respondents Educational Qualification**".

ANOVA					
FinancialLiteracy					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	9.794	3	3.265	13.187	0.000
Within Groups	23.767	96	0.248		
Total	33.561	99			

The statistical output showed a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 and hence Null hypothesis is accepted. ANOVA test proved that, "there is no relation between financial literacy and the respondents Educational Qualification".

-H5 stat that. "There is no association of financial literacy among respondents Monthly Income".

ANOVA					
FinancialLiteracy					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.320	3	0.440	1.310	0.276
Within Groups	32.241	96	0.336		
Total	33.561	99			

The statistical output showed a p-value of 0.276 which is less than 0.05 and hence Null hypothesis is rejected. ANOVA test proved that, "there is relation between financial literacy and the respondents Monthly Income".

IV. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

From the analysis above, we can observe there is relation between financial literacy and the respondents' Age group, Genders, Monthly income. In addition, there is no relation or association between financial literacy and respondents Occupation and their Educational Qualification.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper aims to build a more complete framework of the factors, which influence financial literacy. The results of this study clearly show that in Adilabad District 30% of the village people are facing a lot of problems with financial services. The loan-sanctioned amount to the rural people, utilize the money for various unproductive purposes due to the lack of knowledge about financial planning. This research contributes to the understanding and improving the level of financial literacy of the people. I hope that these conclusions will shed some light for the government and allow them to increase attention to the financial problems of village people.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Chakrabarty, A. K., & Ghosh, K. (2009). Appraisal of a rural co-operative with the thrust on rural development: an empirical study. International Journal of Social Economics.
- [2] Thingalaya, N. K. (1978). Rapporteur's Report on Rural Credit: Structure and Flows. Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics, 33(902-2018-1494), 173-184.
- [3] SINGH, R. (2010). Role of Rural Bank in Economic Development: A Micro-Analysis. Managing Rural Finances in India, 249.
- [4] Reddy, M. M., Akhila, M., Arundhathi, C., Bharathwaj, S. S. B., & Deepak, N. (2017). PERCEPTION OF RURAL HOUSEHOLDS TOWARDS FINANCIAL LITERACY: A STUDY OF KARIMNAGAR DISTRICT OF TELANGANA STATE.
- [5] Priya, R. An Association between Financial Literacy and Investment Behavior of Salaried Individuals: A Study in Telangana State* M. Bala Swamy.
- [6] Vittal, B., & Reddy, M. K. (2019). Comparative study of literacy rate in Telangana state and India using Holt's double exponential smoothing approach.